

Assessment of Articular Cartilage in Traumatic Knee Injuries through T2 Mapping [Cartigram]

Meenakshi Ranjan¹, Vijay Shankar Prasad², Mithilesh Pratap³

¹MD Radiodiagnosis, Department of Radiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²HOD, Department of Radiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor & HOD, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 05-07-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 02-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Ankita Anand

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Traumatic knee injuries are prevalent among active individuals and often result in articular cartilage damage, leading to long-term complications such as osteoarthritis. Traditional imaging techniques have limitations in accurately assessing cartilage integrity. T2 mapping is an advanced MRI technique that quantitatively evaluates cartilage quality, potentially enhancing diagnostic accuracy and patient management.

Aim: This study aims to investigate the relationship between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes in patients with traumatic knee injuries, thereby assessing the clinical utility of T2 mapping as a prognostic tool.

Methods: A retrospective study was conducted involving 200 participants diagnosed with traumatic knee injuries. Medical records were reviewed to extract demographic information, injury details, T2 mapping results, and clinical outcomes, measured using standardized scoring systems such as the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain and the Lysholm Knee Scoring Scale. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0, employing descriptive and inferential statistics to evaluate the correlation between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes.

Results: Of the 200 participants, 40% exhibited normal cartilage quality, while 35% were classified as borderline, and 25% as abnormal. Significant improvements in clinical outcomes were observed, with VAS scores decreasing from a mean of 7.5 at baseline to 2.5 at follow-up and Lysholm scores improving from 52.3 to 82.1. Strong correlations were found between abnormal cartilage quality and higher pain levels ($r = 0.65$) and lower functional scores ($r = -0.70$), indicating that T2 mapping effectively correlates with clinical outcomes.

Conclusion: The findings highlight the critical role of T2 mapping in assessing articular cartilage in traumatic knee injuries. The significant correlations between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes support its utility as a valuable prognostic tool in clinical practice.

Recommendations: Early implementation of T2 mapping in routine assessments of knee injuries is recommended to enhance treatment planning and improve patient outcomes. Future studies should explore the long-term impacts of T2 mapping-guided interventions on recovery and joint health.

Keywords: T2 Mapping, Articular Cartilage, Traumatic Knee Injury, Clinical Outcomes, Osteoarthritis

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Knee injuries are a significant health concern, particularly among active individuals, with traumatic incidents frequently leading to articular cartilage damage. The articular cartilage plays a crucial role in joint function, providing a smooth surface for articulation, distributing loads, and absorbing shock during movement. Damage to this cartilage can lead to debilitating conditions such as osteoarthritis, which affects millions worldwide and is associated with chronic pain and decreased quality of life [1, 2]. Traditional imaging modalities, such as X-rays and MRI, have been used to assess knee injuries; however, they often fall short in providing detailed information about cartilage integrity [3].

Recently, T2 mapping has emerged as a promising advanced imaging technique for evaluating articular cartilage health. T2 mapping quantitatively assesses the relaxation time of water protons in the cartilage matrix, providing insights into its biochemical composition and structural integrity [4]. This technique offers a non-invasive approach to visualize cartilage properties, allowing for early detection of degeneration before structural changes become apparent on conventional imaging [5]. Previous studies have demonstrated that T2 values correlate with histological findings, making T2 mapping a reliable method for evaluating cartilage quality in various knee conditions [6, 7].

Understanding the relationship between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes is vital for improving management strategies for traumatic knee injuries. Recent research has suggested that there is a significant correlation between T2 values and clinical measures of pain and function, indicating that T2 mapping can serve as a valuable prognostic tool in clinical practice [8]. For instance, higher T2 values have been associated with greater pain levels and reduced functional scores, underscoring the relevance of cartilage quality in determining patient outcomes [9].

Despite the advancements in imaging techniques, the clinical utility of T2 mapping in routine practice remains underexplored. There is a pressing need for studies that elucidate the relationship between T2 mapping findings and patient-reported outcomes in individuals with traumatic knee injuries. This research aims to bridge that gap, providing insight into the potential of T2 mapping as an integral part of the diagnostic and therapeutic processes in managing knee injuries.

The understanding of knee cartilage pathology evolves, incorporating advanced imaging techniques like T2 mapping may enhance clinical decision-making and ultimately improve patient outcomes. This study aims to investigate the relationship between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes in patients with traumatic knee injuries, thereby assessing the clinical utility of T2 mapping as a prognostic tool.

Study Design: This study employs a retrospective design.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at Tertiary Care Hospital, where a significant number of patients with knee injuries receive treatment. The data will be sourced from the medical records of patients treated between March 2023 to April 2024.

Participants: A total of 200 participants will be included in this study. Participants will be selected based on the availability of complete medical records that include T2 mapping imaging results and clinical outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants must meet the following criteria:

- Aged 18 years or older.
- Diagnosed with traumatic knee injury, confirmed through clinical assessment and imaging studies (e.g., MRI).
- Underwent T2 mapping imaging (Cartigram) as part of their diagnostic evaluation.
- Available medical records with sufficient follow-up data.

Exclusion Criteria

Participants will be excluded if they:

- Have a history of previous knee surgeries that could affect cartilage assessment.
- Present with inflammatory joint diseases (e.g., rheumatoid arthritis).
- Have undergone other imaging modalities affecting cartilage evaluation within the last six months prior to T2 mapping.
- Are unable to provide informed consent or have incomplete medical records.

Bias: Selection criteria will be strictly followed to ensure a representative sample of participants and reduce bias. Objective imaging data from T2 mapping [Cartigram] will lessen subjective interpretation of the research results. Trained individuals blinded to the study's goals will collect data, reducing information bias. This comprehensive strategy improves study reliability and validity.

Data Collection: Data will be collected from medical records and will encompass a range of important information. This includes demographic details such as age and sex, as well as specifics regarding the traumatic knee injury, including the mechanism of injury and its severity. Additionally, T2 mapping results will be gathered to assess the quality of the cartilage. Clinical outcomes will also be recorded, focusing on pain scores and functional scores at both baseline and follow-up visits. This comprehensive data collection process will provide a robust foundation for evaluating the relationship between T2 mapping findings and clinical outcomes in patients with traumatic knee injuries.

Procedure: Data extraction will involve a thorough review of the medical records of eligible patients to gather relevant information. Following this, imaging analysis will be conducted to evaluate the status of the articular cartilage based on the T2 mapping results. Additionally, follow-up assessments will measure clinical outcomes at the time of T2 mapping and during subsequent follow-up visits, utilizing standardized scoring systems such as the Visual Analog Scale for pain and the Lysholm Knee Scoring Scale. This comprehensive approach ensures a detailed evaluation of both imaging findings and clinical outcomes in the study population.

Statistical Analysis: To ensure accuracy, SPSS version 23.0 will be used for statistical research. The study population's clinical aspects and demographics will be summarised using descriptive statistics. Depending on data distribution, inferential statistics will assess the relationship between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes

using t-tests, chi-square tests, or ANOVA. To determine if T2 mapping outcomes affect clinical scores, Pearson or Spearman correlation analysis will be performed. P-values below 0.05 indicate a substantial relationship between variables.

Results

This study examined 200 traumatic knee injury patients. The demographics of participants are shown in Table 1. The average age of participants was 35.2 years (± 12.1), ranging from 18 to 65 years. Out of 200 participants, 120 (60%) were male and 80 (40%) female. The most prevalent cause of injury was sports (65%), followed by falls (25%), and vehicle accidents (10%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Count (n=200)	Percentage (%)
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	35.2 $\pm$ 12.1	
Gender		
- Male	120	60
- Female	80	40
Mechanism of Injury		
- Sports	130	65
- Fall	50	25
- Vehicular Accident	20	10

Imaging Results: The T2 mapping results indicated varying degrees of cartilage quality among the participants. Based on the T2 values, the cartilage was classified into three categories: normal, borderline, and abnormal.

Table 2: T2 Mapping Results

Cartilage Quality	Count (n=200)	Percentage (%)
Normal	80	40
Borderline	70	35
Abnormal	50	25

Clinical Outcomes: Clinical outcomes were assessed using pain scores and functional scores. At baseline, the mean Visual Analog Scale (VAS) score was 7.5 (± 1.5), indicating moderate to severe pain. The mean Lysholm Knee Scoring Scale score

at baseline was 52.3 (± 10.4), reflecting poor knee function. After follow-up visits, which occurred at 3 and 6 months post-injury, the scores improved significantly, as summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Clinical Outcomes at Baseline and Follow-Up

Measure	Baseline (n=200)	3 Months (n=200)	6 Months (n=200)
VAS Score (mean $\pm$ SD)	7.5 $\pm$ 1.5	4.0 $\pm$ 1.8	2.5 $\pm$ 1.2
Lysholm Score (mean $\pm$ SD)	52.3 $\pm$ 10.4	68.5 $\pm$ 9.7	82.1 $\pm$ 8.9

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed to assess the relationship between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes. A significant correlation was found between T2 mapping results and both the VAS and Lysholm scores.

Table 4: Correlation between T2 Mapping Results and Clinical Outcomes

Measure	VAS Score Correlation Coefficient	Lysholm Score Correlation Coefficient
Normal Cartilage	-0.75	0.65
Borderline Cartilage	-0.50	0.45
Abnormal Cartilage	-0.85	0.75

. The analysis revealed that participants with abnormal cartilage quality had significantly higher VAS scores (mean 8.0 $\pm$ 1.2) compared to those with normal (mean 6.0 $\pm$ 1.3) and borderline cartilage (mean 7.0 $\pm$ 1.5). Similarly, participants with normal cartilage quality exhibited significantly higher Lysholm scores (mean 85.0 $\pm$ 6.5) compared to those with borderline (mean 70.0 $\pm$ 8.5) and abnormal cartilage (mean 60.0 $\pm$ 9.5).

The study included a total of 200 participants with traumatic knee injuries, revealing a mean age of 35.2 years, with a majority being male (60%). The predominant mechanism of injury was sports-related activities, accounting for 65% of cases. This demographic data indicates that younger males are more frequently affected by traumatic knee injuries, which is consistent with previous literature

highlighting the prevalence of such injuries in active populations.

The T2 mapping results indicated varying degrees of cartilage quality among participants, with 40% showing normal cartilage, 35% classified as borderline, and 25% as abnormal. This distribution suggests that a significant portion of patients presented with compromised cartilage quality, emphasizing the importance of early diagnosis and intervention in traumatic knee injuries. The T2 mapping technique demonstrated its effectiveness in differentiating between these categories, allowing for targeted treatment approaches.

Clinical outcomes showed a marked improvement over time. At baseline, participants reported a mean Visual Analog Scale (VAS) score of 7.5, indicating moderate to severe pain. However, by the 6-month follow-up, this score had decreased significantly to 2.5, reflecting substantial pain relief. Additionally, Lysholm Knee Scoring Scale scores improved from a mean of 52.3 at baseline to 82.1 at 6 months, highlighting a considerable enhancement in knee function. These findings underscore the potential for recovery and rehabilitation in patients with traumatic knee injuries when appropriate management strategies are employed.

Statistical analysis demonstrated a significant correlation between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes. Participants with abnormal cartilage exhibited higher VAS scores and lower Lysholm scores compared to those with normal or borderline cartilage. Specifically, the correlation coefficients indicated a strong negative relationship between abnormal cartilage quality and pain levels, while a positive correlation was observed with functional scores. These results suggest that the quality of articular cartilage directly influences both pain perception and functional capacity in patients with knee injuries.

El-Liethy and Kamal (2021) showed that T2 mapping plays a vital role in detecting cartilage lesions, especially in the medial compartments of the knee. This study highlighted how compositional MRI, including T2 mapping, enhances the assessment of early and potentially reversible cartilage damage, particularly in younger populations who present with medial knee pain [10].

Another study by Alsayyad et al. (2020) evaluated the use of T2 mapping in the early detection of osteoarthritis. The research found a highly significant difference in T2 relaxation values between healthy individuals and osteoarthritis patients, suggesting that T2 mapping improves the sensitivity of MRI in detecting early cartilage degeneration, from 82% to 100% sensitivity, in comparison to standard MRI protocols [11].

Furthermore, Shaimaa Shawky et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of T2* mapping, a variation of T2 mapping, in detecting early cartilage lesions in patients who had sustained traumatic knee injuries. This study found that T2* mapping could identify 41 additional lesions that were not visible on routine MRI scans, demonstrating its superiority in early-stage cartilage damage detection [12].

Conclusion

These findings indicate that T2 mapping is a valuable tool for evaluating articular cartilage in patients with traumatic knee injuries. The significant correlations between T2 mapping results and clinical outcomes suggest that the quality of cartilage assessed through T2 mapping directly impacts pain levels and knee function.

References

1. Smith J, Thompson A. Epidemiology of knee injuries: a review of the literature. *J Orthop Surg Res.* 2020;15(1):10-15.
2. Zhang X, Liu Y. Osteoarthritis: a review of its diagnosis and treatment. *Clin Rheumatol.* 2021;40(4):1231-1241.
3. Johnson D, Lee C. Limitations of conventional imaging in knee injury assessment. *Sports Med.* 2019;49(5):787-798.
4. Heo J, Choi Y. Advances in MRI techniques for assessing cartilage quality. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.* 2021;29(3):823-832.
5. Henningsen J, Hede M. T2 mapping in cartilage imaging: a comprehensive review. *Magn Reson Imaging.* 2018;50:5-15.
6. Noyes F, Grood E. T2 mapping: a new approach for assessing cartilage health. *Am J Sports Med.* 2019;47(2):400-409.
7. Watanabe A, Matsumoto T. Histological validation of T2 mapping in articular cartilage. *J Orthop Res.* 2020;38(2):432-440.
8. Kim S, Lee J. Correlation between T2 mapping and clinical outcomes in knee injuries. *Knee Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc.* 2022;30(6):1970-1980.
9. Hwang S, Kim D. Clinical significance of T2 mapping in evaluating knee cartilage. *Surg Radiol Anat.* 2021;43(5):495-503.
10. El-Liethy NE, Kamal H. Advanced compositional imaging T2 mapping sequence in detection of stages of medial knee joint compartments articular cartilage degeneration. *Egyptian Journal of Radiology and Nuclear Medicine.* 2021;52.
11. Alsayyad MAI, Mohamed A, Shehata K, Khattab RT. Role of MRI T2 mapping in the assessment of articular knee cartilage in osteoarthritis. *Ain Shams Medical Journal.* 2020;71:441-55.

12. Shawky S, El-Sharkawy MG, Sakr H, Mansour MG. Comparison of routine magnetic resonance imaging and T2* mapping of

articular cartilage in knee osteoarthritis. QJM: An International Journal of Medicine. 2023.